

An Introduction to Cleft Lip and Palate

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Received: 01-Jan-2022, Manuscript No. jdrp-22-59595; **Editor assigned:** 03-Jan-2022, PreQC No. jdrp-22-59595 (PQ); **Reviewed:** 12-Jan-2022, QC No. jdrp-22-59595 (Q); **Revised:** 12-Jan-2022, Manuscript No. jdrp-22-59595 (R); **Published:** 17-Jan-2022, DOI: 10.4172/jdrp.22.4(1).002

Abstract

Cleft lip and palate are craniofacial congenital abnormalities that impact thousands of children each year throughout the world. These are delicate subjects for discussion, sometimes clouded by the stigma of physical birth defects and cultural myths. The aetiology of cleft lip and palate is discussed in this article, as well as the typical management of patients with oral-facial clefts, which includes lengthy supportive care and an inter-professional team or cleft team approach that extends beyond surgical correction.

Introduction

Cleft lip and palate are craniofacial birth abnormalities that affect roughly 7,000 babies born each year in the United States. The CDC estimates that 2,650 newborns are born with a cleft palate alone and 4,440 babies are born with a cleft lip in the United States per year. Every year, one in 700 babies is born with a cleft lip, cleft palate, or cleft lip and palate.

The most prevalent serial congenital defects affecting the orofacial region are cleft lip and palate. It can occur alone, in various combinations, and/or in conjunction with other congenital malformations, such as congenital heart disease. To achieve functional and aesthetic well-being, patients with oro-facial cleft deformity must be treated at the appropriate time and at the appropriate age. Oral/maxillofacial surgery, otolaryngology, genetics/dysmorphology, speech/language pathology, orthodontics, prosthodontics, and other specialties must all work together to provide coordinated treatment for a child born with a cleft lip and palate.

Cleft lip is caused by the failure of the frontonasal and maxillary processes to fuse, resulting in a cleft in the lip, alveolus, and nasal floor (an incomplete cleft does not extend through the nasal floor, while a complete cleft implies lack of connection between the alar base and the medial labial element).

A cleft of the hard and/or soft palate caused by the failure of the palatal shelves of the maxillary processes to fuse. Clefts appear during the fourth stage of development. The precise location of their appearance is governed by the points at which the fusion of various facial processes failed, which is impacted by the time in embryologic life when some interference with development occurred.

In developing countries, where prenatal care is less advanced or available, a CL/P is more likely to be unexpected, and families rely on religion and folklore to explain the deformity rather than medical explanations from doctors. In India, for example, believe that a CL/P is the result of mis-

deeds committed in a previous life. Witchcraft, God's will, and acting in a behaviour connected with causative power are some of the other religious and cultural ideas about cleft causality (e.g., looking at a child with a facial deformity when pregnant). The lip does not completely fuse during foetal development in cleft lip. Cleft lip and palate are birth malformations that arise during pregnancy, comparable to neural tube defects. Both are caused by the same gene mutation. The malformation can range in severity from minor to severe. When the roof of the mouth does not fully fuse during foetal development, CPO develops; this gap in the palate can extend into the nasal cavity. Cleft lip and CPO can occur independently since embryologic development happens in phases.

Cleft lip and palate embryologic development is the subject of extensive, continuous research, although there is no consensus on the reason. Researchers agree that genetic, dietary, and environmental variables all play a role in their development. Several epidemiological studies have established the importance of genetics in the genesis of cleft lip and palate. Monozygotic twins (60%) have a significantly greater concordance rate than dizygotic twins and siblings, according to numerous studies (5%-10%).

This procedure entails surgically creating a non-obtrusive face, a vocal apparatus that allows comprehensible speech, and a dentition that allows for ideal function and beauty. The concept of a cleft palate squad sprang from this requirement. Because the best care is achieved by combining multiple types of clinical expertise, the team may include members from the following fields:

- Dentistry (orthodontics, oral surgery, paediatric dentistry, and prosthodontics).
- Medicine (genetics, otolaryngology, paediatrics, plastic surgery, and psychiatry).
- Allied health care fields (audiology, nursing, psychology, social work, and speech pathology).

In contrast to the artistic nature of cleft lip repair, cleft palate repair is primarily practical. A collaborative approach has reduced morbidity and subsequent abnormalities produced by the cleft and has mostly focused on speech quality. Soft palate restoration treatments can be utilised alone or in conjunction with hard palate surgeries as needed. To achieve levator muscular realignment, most surgeons currently perform some variation of an intravelar veloplasty vs. a two flap palatoplasty with double opposed z-plasty. Maxillary distraction is becoming more popular in the treatment of severe maxillary retrusion in patients with cleft lip and palate. Children with cleft lip and palate benefit from a collaborative approach to their particular treatment needs. A plastic surgeon-led team should include a speech therapist and orthodontist, as well as easy access to paediatric, ENT, and dental treatment facilities. According to a study of the literature, NAM Cleft lip and palate children benefit from a team approach to particular treatment requirements. When compared to samples that did not receive PSIO, a team led by a plastic surgeon that included a speech therapist and orthodontist and had ready access to paediatric, ENT, and dental treatment facilities did not change skeletal facial growth (pre-surgical infant orthopedics).

The best thing you can do for CLP is to prevent it from happening in the first place. CLP's main goal is to educate parents as well as future moms and fathers. Cleft lip and palate are birth anomalies that impair a variety of structures and functions, including speech difficulties, aesthetics, eating, nutrition, and so on. To attain functional and aesthetic well-being, patients with oro-facial cleft deformity must be treated at the appropriate time and at the appropriate age. Patients with CLP should have their mental health examined and maintained through psychological rehabilitation, and their morale should always be boosted. Although considerable dental treatment may be essential, it should not be made any more comprehensive or complex than is necessary to reach a tolerable level of dental perfection.